

Extraction chromatographic studies of uranium(VI) with high molecular mass amine (aliquat-336)

Keshab K. Dutta and Uday S. Roy*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, India

Manuscript received 22 September 1999, revised 17 April 2000, accepted 24 June 2000

A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of U^{VI} with aliquat-336 (liquid anion exchanger) coated on silica gel as a stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of U^{VI} has been achieved at 1.25–4 M HCl. The effects of different acids with varying concentrations, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger with respect to uranium has been determined. U^{VI} has been separated from the binary, ternary and quaternary mixture of various metal ions. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective.

The need for analytical separation and determination of U^{VI} in trace level has been steadily increasing. THOREX¹ process is used for the separation of uranium from thorium using T.B.P. organophosphorus extractants such as C.M.P. and C.M.P.O. as well as pentaalkylmalonimides have been found to be useful for the extraction of trivalent actinides². Solvent extraction studies of uranium with Alamine 336 and T.O.P.O. mixture³, DB24C8⁴, *N,N*-dialkyl aliphatic amide⁵, Amberlite-AL-2³ in *n*-dodecane have been reported. Most of these methods suffer from emulsification problem. But extraction chromatographic method is useful for the separation of metal ions. The high molecular weight amines in their ammonium salt form have anion exchange ability and also extract anionic metal complexes from aqueous solutions. In continuation of our earlier studies⁶, we present here the results of extraction chromatographic behaviour of U^{VI} on silica gel column impregnated with high molecular weight amine, aliquat-336 from chloride medium.

Results and Discussion

The systematic studies on extraction chromatographic behaviour of U^{VI} with aliquat-336, coated on silica gel in different acids at different concentrations showed that U^{VI} is quantitatively extracted in HCl medium in the concentration range 1.25–4 M, in HNO₃ 7.5 M and above, and in H₂SO₄ even with 4 M concentration not more than 52% extraction was attained. 1.25 M HCl gave best extraction effect.

Stripping agents : After extraction, in order to select specific stripping agent for quantitative elution of U^{VI} from the column, different concentrations of mineral acids such as nitric, sulfuric and salt solutions (ammonium chloride, sodium nitrate) and deionized water were tested. It was observed that quantitative recovery of U^{VI} is possible with

0.05–0.1 M NaNO₃, upto 0.5 M NH₄Cl, upto 4 M HNO₃ and also with deionized water. Of these eluents, deionized water was found to be most suitable and used for elution of U^{VI} in further steps of experiment.

Separation of U^{VI} from binary mixture : It was possible to separate U^{VI} from several metal ions in binary mixtures by exploiting the difference in acid concentration and also by using selective eluting agents. In binary mixtures with U^{VI} in 1.25 M HCl, Th^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Pm^{III} and Sm^{III} passed unextracted through the column with the mobile phase. Extracted U^{VI} was, however, eluted with deionized water and estimated complexometrically with EDTA. Binary mixtures containing U^{VI} and Cd^{II}, Fe^{III}, Pd^{II}, Ga^{III}, Cr^{III} and Pb^{II} were passed separately through the column at 1.25 M HCl where all the diverse ions were co-extracted with U^{VI}. All the diverse metal ions, except Cd^{III}, were eluted first with 7.5 M HNO₃, followed by U^{VI} with deionized water. In case of Cd^{II}, U^{VI} was eluted first with deionized water and then Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO₃. Separation of Hg^{II} and In^{III} from their binary mixtures with U^{VI} was achieved by passing their solutions in 1 M HNO₃ and 3 M HCl, respectively, through the column whereby the former ions were extracted leaving U^{VI} in the mobile phase. After separation, all the metal ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA. The results of binary separations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Separation of U^{VI} from binary mixtures

U^{VI} taken = 2.62 mg

Metal ion	Wt. of metal (mg)		Recovery of U ^{VI} %	Eluent used
	Added	Recovered		
Th ^{VI}	1.97	1.96	100	–
Ce ^{VI}	1.70	1.68	100.3	–

Table-1 (contd.)

Fe ^{III}	2.24	2.22	100	7.5 M HNO ₃
Zr ^{IV}	1.50	1.51	100	-
Ga ^{III}	1.00	1.04	100	7.5 M HNO ₃
Pd ^{II}	1.78	1.77	100	7.5 M HNO ₃
La ^{III}	2.02	2.00	100.3	-
Pr ^{III}	2.05	2.02	100	-
Nd ^{III}	1.56	1.53	100.3	-
Pm ^{III}	2.15	2.16	99.6	-
Sm	1.64	1.63	100	-
In ^{III}	2.65	2.63	100.3	7.5 M HNO ₃
Cd ^{II}	2.90	2.91	100	7.5 M NaNO ₃
Pb ^{II}	2.69	2.68	100	7.5 M HNO ₃
Cr ^{II}	2.44	2.43	100	-
Hg ^{II}	1.94	1.93	99.6	H ₂ O

Table-2 (contd.)

8. ^b	Th ^{IV}	1.97	100	H ₂ O
	Ce ^{IV}	1.7	99	-
	Pb ^{II}	2.69	100	7.5 M HNO ₃
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100	H ₂ O

^a1.25 M HCl. ^b0.4 M HNO₃.

Experimental

An Elico L1-120 pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a chromatographic column (Borosil) were used.

The liquid anion exchanger, aliquat -336 (Fluka, AG), a high molecular mass synthetic quaternary amine (tricaprylammonium chloride) was used as such. A stock solution of uranium(VI) (5.24 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving uranyl nitrate in distilled water and standardised complexometrically using xylenol orange as indicator. The ion exchange material was prepared following literature method⁷.

Extraction procedure : 1.25 M HCl (20 ml) was passed through the column (0.8 × 6.5 cm). An aliquot containing 2.62 mg of U^{VI} was passed through the column (1.25 M HCl) at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. After extraction, U^{VI} was stripped with different acids, bases, salts of various concentrations and demineralized water. Water was found to be the best stripping agent. The amount of U^{VI} was determined complexometrically.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures (20–40°) measuring milligram equivalents of OH⁻ absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in the chloride form⁸. The liberated chloride was titrated against standard AgNO₃ solution using potassium chromate as indicator⁹. The exchange capacity was found to be 0.57 mg/g dry exchanger.

References

1. "Reactor Hand Book, Fuel Reprocessing", eds. S. M. Stroller and R. B. Richards, Interscience, New York, 1961, Vol. 2.
2. C. Musikus, "Proc. Nucl. and Radiochem. Symp. (NUCAR-95)", 1995.
3. C. Sriram, R. V. Raghavan and V. K. Manchanda, "Proc. Nucl. and Radiochem. Symp. (NUCAR-99)", 1999.
4. B. S. Mohite, J. M. Patil and D. N. Zambare, *J. Radio Nucl. Chem.*, 1993, 170, 215.
5. C. M. Musicus, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, 14, 197.
6. P. K. Saha and U. S. Roy, *Chem. Environ. Res.*, 1997, 1-2, 6.
7. S. N. Bhosale and S. M. Khopkar, *Talanta*, 1979, 26, 889.
8. K. Mitra and U. S. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, 72, 279.
9. A. Pusparajan and M. Sudarsan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 925.

Separation of U^{VI} from multicomponent mixtures : The proposed method was applied to separate U^{VI} from several ternary and quaternary mixtures and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Separation of U^{VI} from multicomponent synthetic mixtures
eluent volume = 25 ml

Sl no.	Metal ions	Wt. added	Recovery %	Eluent used
1. ^a	Th ^{IV}	1.97	99.4	-
	Pb ^{II}	2.69	99.6	7.5 M HNO ₃
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100	H ₂ O
2. ^a	Th ^{IV}	1.97	99.4	-
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.3	H ₂ O
	Cd ^{II}	2.9	100.2	0.5 M NaNO ₃
3. ^a	Zr ^{IV}	1.51	100	-
	Pb ^{II}	2.69	99.6	7.5 M HNO ₃
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100	H ₂ O
4. ^b	Th ^{IV}	1.97	99	H ₂ O
	Zr ^{IV}	1.5	99.3	-
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100	H ₂ O
5. ^b	Th ^{IV}	1.97	100.5	H ₂ O
	Zr ^{IV}	1.7	99.4	-
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.3	H ₂ O
6. ^b	Th ^{IV}	1.97	100	H ₂ O
	Pr ^{III}	2.05	100.9	-
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100	H ₂ O
7. ^b	Th ^{IV}	1.97	99	H ₂ O
	Zr ^{IV}	1.5	99.4	-
	Pb ^{II}	2.69	100.3	7.5 M HNO ₃
	U ^{VI}	2.62	100.3	H ₂ O